

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

EXTRACTION OF HUMIC ACIDS BY THE PYROPHOSPHATE METHOD

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information on an effective method for the extraction of humic acids by the pyrophosphate method of six coal objects titled "Shrub", "Fon-Yagnob", "Ziddi", "Sayad", "Nazar-Ailok" and "Kurtegin" to investigated and evaluate the source of humic acids. The study confirms that moisture content, ash content, bitumen, and the number of humic acids vary from coals sources. The humic acids were isolated and obtained from the composition of brown and hard coals by the extraction method, physicochemical studies, conformational interpretation, and structural and functional characteristics of complex compounds of humic acids

Keywords: humic acids, coals, natural compounds, extraction method, chemical composition.

Introduction

Natural complex organic compounds in the form of clusters are called humic substances (HS). They form a separate class of natural compounds and are found as organic products in soil, roots, natural waters, peat, and natural coal. Molecules of humic substances include various functional groups, such as -COOH, -CO, -OH, NH₂, NH, etc., and also form compounds with aromatic fragments with various ecotoxicants, such as metals, radionuclides and organic compounds [1-4].

They contribute to the growth of plants, are responsible for the structure and physical-chemical properties of soil, and are involved in the majority of surface phenomena that occur in soils. With such a large impact, they can affect the process of movement of heavy metals, radionuclides and organic ecotoxicants, preventing their spread in the form of a geochemical flood. Given this feature, they are used as sorbents for the purification of groundwater from natural ecotoxicants [6].

Materials and methods

The investigated source of humic acids is six coal objects of our country: coals "Shrub", "Fon-Yagnob", "Ziddi", "Sayad", "Nazar-Ailok" and "Kurtegin". First of all, we had to determine the main characteristics of coal: moisture content, amount of bitumen, and greyness. Then we began to isolate humic acids by extraction. The results obtained are presented in Table 1.

The moisture content of coals was determined by taking samples of coal and heating them in drying cabinets at a temperature of 100–103°C for 1 hour in a glass bottle. Then it was cooled to room temperature in a desiccator and weighed on an analytical balance. We

repeated this experiment three times and achieved a difference of 0.05%.

We also used the Hoffmann method to determine the hygroscopic moisture content of coal. This constant humidity ranged from 3 to 5%, it is not surprising that this difference depends on their metamorphism.

To free coal samples from bituminous compounds, their dry powder was extracted with toluene using a Soxhlet apparatus. We expressed the amount of bitumen as a percentage.

To determine the ash content, the coal was burned in a muffle furnace at a temperature of 700–800°C for 3 hours, cooled to room temperature, and the ash residue was weighed on an analytical balance.

The chemical elements in brown coal and black coal were determined by the atomic emission spectroscopic method. The thermogram of humic acid samples was recorded on a DSC-204 F1 differential scanning calorimeter.

Humic acids from coal samples were studied by extraction with an alkaline solution of pyrophosphate (Na₄P₂O₇) and an alkaline dimethyl sulfoxide method. This method was slightly modified as a result of our additional processing, which gave a good result in terms of KG yield.

To evaluate this method, bituminous and dried coal was placed in a chemical flask (A) and treated with an alkaline solution of pyrophosphate (Na₄P₂O₇)₂ [(Na₄P₂O₇ + NaOH + H₂O)], stirred for a certain time and separated its aqueous solution, the resulting solution was transferred to the second flask (B), the rest of it, which appeared in the form of a suspension, was centrifuged, its precipitate was washed with a 1% NaOH

solution, and after centrifugation this solution was also transferred to flask B. The remaining precipitate was washed twice with 1% NaOH solution and centrifuged.

This solution was also poured into flask B. In flask B, the collected solution was poured into a 1-liter volumetric flask and topped up with water to the mark. 100 ml of the solution was taken from it, transferred to a flask, and 5% HCl solution was added to it to pH 3-4. Thus, after a few minutes, humic acids precipitated out of solution. The precipitate formed was dried and its mass was determined. Then the resulting amount of humic acids was burned in a muffle furnace at a temperature of 700-800°C (in a crucible heated to constant

weight and weighed) and the mass of ash was determined.

According to the formula below, the ash content of coal was calculated

here:

$$m_y = m_3 \frac{100 - (W^a + A^a)}{100} \quad (1)$$

m_3 – is the weight of the coal sample, g;

W^a - analytical moisture content of coal in %

A^a - is the ash content of the coal sample, %.

Results and discussions

Table 1.

Physical properties and output of humic acids of coal from various deposits in Tajikistan

Name of deposits	Quantity, %					
	Humidity	Ash content	Bitumen	* Yield of humic acids	** Yield of humic acids	Ash content of humic acids
Shurob	7.2-11.59	10.01-13.36	11.1-14.70	19-22.66		2.43-5.94
Fon-Yagnob	19.8	2.28-9.5	18.18	15.4	19.90	0.8
Ziddi	5-19.92	2.18-8.96	7.14	16.5		4.37
Nazar-Ailok	2.65	2.6-3.55	2.04-5.54	9.54		0.26
Sayod	6.92	16.4-22.11	15.21	16.6	17.50	0.04
Kurtegin	2.2-9.83	3.0-4.5	3.0-3.62	13.19		0.25

* - extraction of humic acids by pyrophosphate method

** - extraction of humic acids by the classical method

As can be seen from Table 1, the results of moisture content, ash content, bituminosity and the amount of humic acids in the studied coals differ from each other. For example, their moisture content ranges from 2.2% to 20%. Coal "Nazar-Ailok" has the lowest humidity. Coal with a high moisture content is considered "Ziddi" coal.

Ash content analysis showed that Sayad coal had a high ash content, 16.4-22.11%. And here the coal

"Nazar-Ailok" is low-ash. Such a difference compared to other coals may depend on the geomorphology (relief) of the location and the natural environment [5–9].

The bituminosity of the listed coals is also different and ranges from 3% to 14%. For example, bitumen in the Nazar-Ailok coal is from 2 to 5%, and in the Shorob coal - from 11 to 14%. If we describe these anomalies (against the rule) in the form of a diagram, then we will see the difference.

Figure 1. Diagram of bitumen content of coal deposits: "N-Nazar-Aylo"; "Z-Ziddi"; "Sh-Shurob"; "S-Sayed"; "F-Fon-Yagnob"; "K-Kurtegin"

Although the pyrophosphate method is difficult, it gives a relatively high yield, since humic acids never dissolve in water and aqueous solutions. They have the structure of an amorphous yellowish powder. No signs of dissolution in organic solvents were found. However, they dissolve very well in alkalis and alkaline solutions and retain their biologically active properties. This, of course, depends on the substances that are in the complex cluster of the humic acid structure in its outer (third) layer, which consists mainly of polar semi-functional substances and has more -COOH group than other compounds. This group includes compounds - large molecular organic acids, amino acids, peptides, proteins, hydroxy acids, phenols and others. These substances form stable complexes with heavy metals in the form of complex compounds.

Some scientist confirms that in addition to this group of substances, heterocyclic or amine groups also participate in complex formation. In our opinion, amino acids and peptides play an important role in this process.

Conclusion

Thus, humic acids were isolated from the composition of brown and hard coals by the extraction method, physicochemical studies, and conformational interpretation, structural and functional characteristics of complex compounds of humic acids were obtained. Moreover, the study revealed that the content of humic acids from different coal sources from local places is able to widely use as an agent against toxicants in ecosystems and medicine.

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